

PRINCIPAL MASTER DIAGRAMS APPROACH TO FATIGUE LIFE PREDICTION OF COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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1 Introduction

For accurate fatigue analysis of structural components made of carbon fiber-reinforced plastics (CFRPs), it is a prerequisite to quantify the influence of loading mode on the sensitivity to fatigue of the composites employed. To do that, however, a large number of fatigue tests under many different kinds of cyclic loading conditions are needed, which consumes considerable time and cost. For this reason, it is required to develop a time and cost-saving engineering procedure for predicting the fatigue strengths (S-N relationships) of composites under different loading conditions, with reasonable accuracy, on the basis of the static strengths in tension and compression and a limited number of constant amplitude fatigue test data.

The present study aims to develop a new fatigue model for unidirectional composites by a combination of a new fatigue failure criterion and a constant fatigue life (CFL) diagram approach. First, constant amplitude fatigue tests are performed on coupon specimens of a unidirectional carbon/epoxy laminate at different stress ratios in the longitudinal and transverse directions and in a shear dominated off-axis direction, respectively. On the basis of the fatigue data obtained, the principal CFL diagrams for the unidirectional CFRP laminate are identified. Then, the anisomorphic CFL diagram approach [1] is tested for the issue of predicting the principal CFL diagrams, and the accuracy of predictions using this method is evaluated. An extended version of the anisomorphic CFL diagram approach is also applied to obtain better description of the principal CFL diagrams for the unidirectional CFRP laminate. Finally, the fatigue failure criterion combined with the principal master diagrams is applied to predicting the off-axis S-N relationships of the unidirectional composite for different stress ratios,

and the accuracy of prediction is evaluated by comparing with experimental results.

2 Material and Testing Procedure

The material used in this study was a unidirectional T700S/2592 carbon/epoxy laminate fabricated from the prepreg tape P3252S-20 (TORAY). Six kinds of coupon specimens with different fiber orientations ($\theta = 0, 10, 15, 30, 45$ and 90°) were prepared. Constant amplitude fatigue tests were performed under load control at different stress ratios. Fatigue load was applied to off-axis coupon specimens in a sinusoidal waveform at room temperature.

3 Experimental Results

The longitudinal, transverse and in-plane shear CFL diagrams for the unidirectional CFRP laminate were identified on the basis of the experimental results, and they are shown by symbols in Figs. 1 (a)-(c), respectively, for different constant values of life: $N_f = 10^1, 10^2, 10^3, 10^4, 10^5$ and 10^6 . The dashed lines in these figures indicate the predictions using the method that are discussed later on. It is seen that the longitudinal CFL diagram shown in Fig. 1(a) is similar in shape to the CFL diagrams observed for multidirectional CFRP laminates [1], and thus it can be described using the anisomorphic CFL diagram. In contrast, a significant distortion is involved in the transverse and in-plane shear CFL diagrams (Figs. 1(b) and 1(c)), indicating that a significant change in mean stress sensitivity in fatigue has occurred. The latter observation suggests the need for a modification to the original two-segment anisomorphic CFL diagram approach so that a modified CFL diagram allows accommodating itself

(a) Longitudinal CFL diagram ($\theta = 0^\circ$)

(b) Transverse CFL diagram ($\theta = 90^\circ$)

(c) In-plane shear CFL diagram

Fig.1. Principal CFL diagrams

to such a significant change in mean stress sensitivity.

4 Modeling of Principal CFL Diagrams

The CFL diagrams for composites that are affected by a significant change in mean stress sensitivity in fatigue can be coped with by inserting transitional segments in the anisomorphic CFL diagram, while it impairs the simplicity of the anisomorphic CFL diagram approach. In the previous study [2], we found that the insertion of two transitional segments in the right and left neighborhoods of the critical

stress ratio greatly improves the accuracy of description of the off-axis CFL diagrams of a unidirectional composite, regardless of fiber orientation. In this study, we adopt the four-segment extension of the anisomorphic CFL diagram approach for description of the principal CFL diagrams for unidirectional composites.

The four-segment anisomorphic CFL diagram [2], which is a most general CFL diagram in the context of the anisomorphic CFL diagram approach, can be described by using different formulas on the four subintervals of the total interval of mean stress $[\sigma_c, \sigma_T]$: I. $[\sigma_m^{(\chi_R)}, \sigma_T]$; II. $[\sigma_m^{(\chi)}, \sigma_m^{(\chi_R)}]$; III. $[\sigma_m^{(\chi_L)}, \sigma_m^{(\chi)}]$; IV. $[\sigma_c, \sigma_m^{(\chi_L)}]$. In line with the formulation of the three-segment anisomorphic CFL diagram, it is natural to describe a four-segment anisomorphic CFL diagram by means of the following piecewise-defined function:

I. Tension dominated zone ($\sigma_m^{(\chi_R)} \leq \sigma_m \leq \sigma_T$):

$$-\frac{\sigma_a - \sigma_a^{(\chi_R)}}{\sigma_a^{(\chi_R)}} = \left(\frac{\sigma_m - \sigma_m^{(\chi_R)}}{\sigma_T - \sigma_m^{(\chi_R)}} \right)^{2-\psi_{\chi_R} k_T} \quad (1)$$

II. Right transitional zone ($\sigma_m^{(\chi)} \leq \sigma_m < \sigma_m^{(\chi_R)}$):

$$-\frac{\sigma_a - \sigma_a^{(\chi_R)}}{\sigma_a^{(\chi_R)} - \sigma_a^{(\chi)}} = \frac{\sigma_m - \sigma_m^{(\chi_R)}}{\sigma_m^{(\chi)} - \sigma_m^{(\chi_R)}} \quad (2)$$

III. Left transitional zone ($\sigma_m^{(\chi_L)} \leq \sigma_m < \sigma_m^{(\chi)}$):

$$-\frac{\sigma_a - \sigma_a^{(\chi)}}{\sigma_a^{(\chi)} - \sigma_a^{(\chi_L)}} = \frac{\sigma_m - \sigma_m^{(\chi)}}{\sigma_m^{(\chi_L)} - \sigma_m^{(\chi)}} \quad (3)$$

IV. Compression dominated zone ($\sigma_c \leq \sigma_m < \sigma_m^{(\chi_L)}$):

$$-\frac{\sigma_a - \sigma_a^{(\chi_L)}}{\sigma_a^{(\chi_L)}} = \left(\frac{\sigma_m - \sigma_m^{(\chi_L)}}{\sigma_c - \sigma_m^{(\chi_L)}} \right)^{2-\psi_{\chi_L} k_C} \quad (4)$$

where ψ_{χ_R} and ψ_{χ_L} designate the fatigue strength ratios associated with the right and left sub-critical

stress ratios, χ_R and χ_L , respectively, and they are defined as

$$\psi_{\chi_R} = \sigma_{\max}^{(\chi_R)} / \sigma_T \quad (5)$$

$$\psi_{\chi_L} = \sigma_{\min}^{(\chi_L)} / \sigma_C \quad (6)$$

The critical and sub-critical stress ratios satisfy the condition $-\infty \leq \chi_L \leq \chi \leq \chi_R \leq 0$. The fatigue strength ratios associated with the critical and sub-critical stress ratios are described by means of the monotonic continuous functions of the number of cycles to failure. Note that $\sigma_a^{(\chi_R)} + \sigma_m^{(\chi_R)} = \sigma_{\max}^{(\chi_R)}$, $\sigma_a^{(\chi_L)} + \sigma_m^{(\chi_L)} = \sigma_{\max}^{(\chi_L)}$ and $\sigma_a^{(\chi)} + \sigma_m^{(\chi)} = \sigma_{\max}^{(\chi)}$.

If either of these two supplementary stress ratios is assumed to coincide with the critical stress ratio, the four-segment model is reduced to a three-segment model that was tested in an earlier study [3]. Obviously, it further reduces to the original two-segment model [1] if both of the two supplementary stress ratios agree with the critical stress ratio and accordingly the associated transitional segments are both removed.

A particular case in which $\chi_R = 0$ and $\chi_L = -\infty$ is hereafter called the standard four-segment anisomorphic CFL diagram. Similarly, when referring to the standard three-segment anisomorphic CFL diagram, we implicitly assume that the second critical stress ratio is specified by either of these stress ratios.

The dashed lines in Figs. 1 (a)-(c) indicate the principal CFL envelopes predicted using the four-segment anisomorphic CFL diagram. A good agreement can be seen between the prediction and experimental results.

5 Multiaxial Fatigue Strength Model Based on the Principal CFL Diagrams

To predict the fatigue lives of orthotropic composites, different forms of fatigue failure criteria based on the assumption of principal fatigue strengths have been developed by Hashin and Rotem [4], Sims and Brogdon [5], and Hahn [6]. The Hashin-Rotem fatigue model is an extension of the

Hashin-Rotem static failure criterion. The Sims-Brogdon fatigue model is based on the Tsai-Hill static failure criterion. The Hahn fatigue model is based on the maximum stress criterion for static failure. The static failure criteria that these fatigue models underlie assume that they are applied to proportional loading either in tension or in compression. Thus, they cannot deal with the strength differential between tension and compression in a unified manner.

When predicting the fatigue lives of composites for any operational load spectra, on the other hand, we need to distinguish not only between the static strengths in tension and compression, but also between the fatigue strengths in tension and compression dominated cyclic loading. This practical requirement should be fulfilled by development of a fatigue model that considers the static and fatigue strength differentials between tension and compression. In this study, we attempt to develop a fatigue model on the basis of the modified Tsai-Hill failure criterion that can distinguish between the off-axis strengths in tension and compression [7].

The modified Tsai-Hill failure criterion that considers the SD effects in all of the principal strengths has been formulated as follows [7]:

[I] Off-axis tensile loading ($\sigma_{22} > 0$):

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{X_T}\right)^2 - \frac{\sigma_{11}\sigma_{22}}{X_T^2} + \left(\frac{\sigma_{22}}{Y_T}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{12}}{S_T}\right)^2 = 1 \quad (7)$$

[II] Off-axis compression loading ($\sigma_{22} < 0$):

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{X_C}\right)^2 - \frac{\sigma_{11}\sigma_{22}}{X_C^2} + \left(\frac{\sigma_{22}}{Y_C}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{12}}{S_T - \mu_L \sigma_{22}}\right)^2 = 1 \quad (8)$$

where μ_L is a material constant that characterizes the in-plane shear SD effect.

The modified Tsai-Hill failure criterion mentioned above is extended to a fatigue model. For T-T and C-C loading, the aim is accomplished simply by replacing the principal static strengths with the

Fig.2. Prediction of off-axis S-N relationships

principal fatigue strengths of the composite. During T-C loading, however, the sign of transverse stress changes. Therefore, we need to define the procedure for judging fatigue failure under T-C loading. In this study, fatigue failure for the right segment partitioned by the off-axis critical stress $\chi(\theta) = \sigma_c(\theta) / \sigma_T(\theta)$ in the $\sigma_m - \sigma_a$ plane is judged by means of the tension-dominated fatigue failure criterion, while for the left segment it is judged by means of the compression-dominated fatigue failure criterion.

The solid lines in Fig. 2 indicate the off-axis S-N curves for $R = 0.5$ that were predicted using the proposed off-axis fatigue failure criterion. In the case $R = 0.5$, it is seen that the proposed approach successfully predicts the off-axis S-N relationships for all fiber orientations. Satisfactory predictions have also been made for different stress ratios.

6. Conclusions

The in-plane principal CFL diagrams for a unidirectional CFRP laminate were first identified. Then, a new four-segment CFL diagram approach keeping the spirit of the anisomorphic CFL diagram approach was developed to describe the principal CFL diagrams. The validity of the four-segment CFL diagram approach was evaluated for the accuracy of prediction not only of the principal CFL diagrams but also of the off-axis CFL diagrams for other fiber orientations. Finally, a new engineering methodology for predicting the off-axis fatigue lives of unidirectional composites using the tension-compression asymmetric fatigue strength model in

conjunction with the principal CFL diagrams was proposed. It was demonstrated that the fatigue failure criterion allows accurately and efficiently predicting the off-axis fatigue lives of a unidirectional composite for any fiber orientation and for any stress ratio of fatigue loading.

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